

BELIEFS AND ATTITUDES OF BRAZILIANS TOWARD VARIETIES OF THE SPANISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT. This study¹³ examines the linguistic beliefs and attitudes of 33 Brazilian speakers of Spanish as a foreign language regarding five varieties of the Spanish language: Andean variety, Rio-Platense variety, Mexican variety, Peninsular variety, and a foreign variety. Based on the theoretical framework of linguistic beliefs and attitudes by Méndez Guerrero (2022), Pereira and Costa (2012), Moreno Fernández (2009), and Lambert and Lambert (1975), it is proposed that the most prestigious varieties will be the Peninsular and Rio-Platense varieties. The Peninsular variety is considered the most prestigious among the varieties. In the case of the Rio-Platense variety, it receives many positive evaluations in attitude research due to its salient features. Additionally, it is proposed that there will be a high level of linguistic insecurity among the participants, given that they are speakers of Spanish as a foreign language. It was found that, in line with the hypotheses presented, the varieties that received more positive evaluations were the Rio-Platense and Peninsular varieties. Regarding the second hypothesis, the data showed that the majority of the research participants demonstrated linguistic security.

KEYWORDS: linguistic beliefs and attitudes; linguistic insecurity; varieties of Spanish; Spanish language; speakers of Spanish as a foreign language; linguistic assessments; level of identification of varieties.

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Due to its subjective nature, studies on linguistic beliefs and attitudes are strong allies in understanding linguistic issues related to the recognition of «affective and cognitive reactions that individuals manifest in the hypotheses and evaluative judgments they make» (Méndez Guerrero, 2022, p. 396). Attitudes interact with linguistic practices, as pointed out by Pereira and Costa (2012), «the regression/disappearance of a language, language revitalization policies, linguistic security/insecurity, as well as approaches to language teaching» (Pereira and Costa, 2012, p. 172), and also, the conditions under which these attitudes are produced determine the ideas we have about languages and the people who speak those languages.

In light of the above, this work aims to analyse the level of identification of Spanish language varieties (Andean, Peninsular, Rioplatense, and Mexican) by Brazilian speakers of Spanish as a foreign language, using audio recordings and a questionnaire created as a research instrument for this purpose. In addition to the four Spanish language varieties, we present audio recordings of Brazilians who speak Spanish as a foreign language to discover if Brazilians are capable of identifying their own variety.

An attitude is, as presented by Lambert and Lambert (1975), «an organized and coherent way of thinking, feeling, and reacting to people, groups, social issues, or more generally, to any event in the environment». According to the authors, «the essential components of attitudes are thoughts and beliefs, feelings and emotions, as well as tendencies to react» (Lambert and Lambert, 1975, p. 100).

As observed, the way social psychology views beliefs and attitudes influences how speakers behave in social interactions in general. Discussions on this topic shifted to sociolinguistics in the 1980s and 90s. From this point on, this area of knowledge began to be developed to better understand the linguistic beliefs, attitudes, and representations that speakers have, since «attitudes are manifested towards both one's own linguistic varieties and uses as well as towards others» (Moreno Fernández, 2009, p. 179). Therefore, any speaker is capable of expressing opinions, feelings, and preferences about the way others speak, as well as about their own. Any speaker can

identify whether a given variety is familiar or distant from their own when listening to others speak.

A research instrument created and inspired by the instrument used in the PRECAVES Project – Project for the Study of Beliefs and Attitudes about Spanish Varieties in the 21st Century was employed. This instrument includes an online questionnaire created through the Google Forms platform. Among the participants, 19 are women and 14 are men.

Regarding the results, there is a higher proportion of proper identification for the Peninsular variety (63.6% for the female voice) and the Rioplatense variety (48.5% for the male voice). In third place, we have foreign voices with 36.4% proper recognition for the male voice and 18.2% for the female voice. The low level of recognition for the foreign female voice may be related to the fact that this voice adopts an accent more similar to that of natives, making it difficult to be recognized as foreign. The least recognized variety was the Andean, with only 12.1% proper identification for the male voice and 15.2% for the female voice.

The varieties that were better evaluated were the Mexican (male voice) with an average of 3.28, considering a scale from 1 to 4, and the Rioplatense with 3.24 for the female voice and 3.21 for the male voice. Surprisingly, the Peninsular variety (female voice) received the most negative evaluations, with an average of 2.96, as this variety is usually the highest-rated in studies in the field and is almost always cited as the most prestigious variety of the Spanish language. We can infer that this result occurred this way due to the geographical distance of the research participants from this variety. Latin American varieties are geographically closer, facilitating the recognition.

Regarding linguistic insecurity, 19 out of the 33 research participants reported speaking Spanish well, while 13 stated that they do not speak this language well. One participant mentioned that it depends on the context, as they would have to adapt their way of speaking and do not feel comfortable with some stylistic variables of the language.

We conclude that, according to Méndez Guerrero (2022, p. 377), the greater identification of the Peninsular Spanish variety is due to the tradition of considering

this variety as a reference, an idea that still prevails in some contexts and/or social groups.

Regarding the Rioplatense variety, it is characterized by unique pronunciation aspects, such as the use of «voseo» (the use of the second-person singular pronoun «vos» instead of «tú»), and sound characteristics, as the countries in the Rio de la Plata region received many European immigrants, especially Italians. These features contribute to an accurate identification of the variety (Andión Herrero, 2004, p. 41–42).

From the level of recognition of a variety, speakers express attitudes – positive or negative. We believe it could be interesting for future studies to pay attention to these types of attitudes expressed towards each variety and to seek an understanding of the factors that determine such attitudes.

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